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Confined channels and collapse features in Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos (Mars): hints for a volcano-tectonic origin

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Introduction

Chaotic terrains are wide areas on Mars characterized by the disruption of the bedrock in polygonal blocks, separated by deep fractures and grabens. The most accepted process as the origin of the disruption involves a catastrophic collapse, but the nature of the collapse itself is still debated and several mechanisms of formation were proposed such as: magma-cryosphere interactions [1], changes in pressure within the aquifer [2], dewatering of fluids from buried hydrated deposits [3], and melting of buried ice lake [4]. We investigate a possible major role played by volcano-tectonic processes based on the evidences observed in Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos, two adjacent Chaotic terrains located in the equatorial zone, between Valles Marineris and Arabia Terra (Fig.1).

Data and methods

The observations we are carrying on are made on CTX and HiRISE images from the MRO spacecraft. The raw images are processed on ISIS3 (USGS) and the DEMs are obtained through ASP (Nasa)[5]. The DEMs are bundle-adjusted to the global topography. Measurements and mapping are performed on ArcMap (ESRI suite).

Conclusions

The fissures, grabens and pit chains observed in Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos may represent the surface expression of a mazy network of lava conduits, departing from a magma chamber in depth and facilitated by regional stresses during the intrusion to reach the surface.

Fig. 3: 3D-view (IHS false color, HRSC h1947_0000.ihs.52) showing y-shaped conjunctions between fissures (white arrow) and a lava flow nearby (black arrow).

Fig. 4: The area is pervasively affected by pits (black arrow) and pit chains (white arrow), mapped in Fig. 6 as pitted areas and pit chains respectively. CTX mosaic.

Fig. 7: Interpretative sketch (not to scale) of the piecemeal caldera collapse as a formation mechanism for the two studied Chaotic terrains and the structures therein.

Fig. 6: Mapping of the structures occurring across Arsinoes Chaos and Pyrrhae Chaos. CTX mosaic.

References

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Fig. 1: Location of Arsinoes Chaos and Pyrrhae Chaos

Fig. 2: Elongated depression occurring close to lava flows (black arrows) and pit chains (white arrows). CTX mosaic.

Fig. 5: The elongated depressions, coalescent with grabens, show concentric (in light blue) and radial (in yellow) orientations in proximity of the ring fault (in red). CTX mosaic.

Discussion

The complex geological setting of Arsinoes and Pyrrhae Chaos is characterized by the occurrence of extensive networks of fractures and grabens shaping the disrupted morphology into an alternation of mesas and knobs. Around the rim of the Chaotic terrains (henceforth called *ring fault*) elongated graben-like depressions were observed (Fig. 2-3-4-5) and mapped (Fig. 6).

We exclude a fluvial origin for these channels since they lack braided or meandering morphologies, they show blind ends and do not seem to follow the topography.

The hints suggesting a volcano-tectonic origin include:

- Linear or slightly sinuous morphology consistent with fissure vents; (Fig. 2-3-4-5);
- Lava flows occurring nearby the fissures (Fig. 2 and 3);
- Associated pit chains, often coalescent with the fissures (Fig. 2-4), interpreted as fissure systems by [6];
- The fissures are coalescent also with the grabens bordering the polygonal blocks of the Chaotic terrain or they present a gradational transition (Fig. 5);
- The grabens are often orthogonal each other and interrupt at the fault ring. Around the fault ring, both concentric and radial structures were recognized (Fig. 5);
- Y-shaped conjunctions suggestive of inflation (Fig. 3-5)

If an intricate system of lava conduits is assumed to explain the occurrence of the fissures/grabens and pit chains, we can also investigate the possibility that the whole collapse was caused in first place by volcano-tectonic processes.

On Earth, polygonal blocks and systems of concentric + radial fissures are originated in the frame of a particular caldera collapse called *chaotic* or *piecemeal* [7][8][9]. The chaotic collapse (Fig. 7) would have been triggered by repeated inflation and deflation of a putative magma chamber in depth under the terrain, but also phreatomagmatic activity needs to be further investigated.